

1 ILF2 and ILF3 connect Xist to UNG and DNA primase 2 at the DNA with SLBP.
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7 We describe here a requirement for uracil DNA glycosylase (UNG) in transformation as part of a
8 transcriptional complex at the DNA containing ILF2 and ILF3, DNA primase 2 and the stem loop binding
9 protein SLBP.

10 Citations

11 1. Nilsen, H., Rosewell, I., Robins, P., Skjelbred, C.F., Andersen, S., Slupphaug, G., Daly, G.,
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